

Social-Emotional Competence Is Imperative For Elementary School Students

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Abstract

Social- Emotional Competence (SEC) is one of the most important investigated area of everybody's life, especially in young children in present scenario. To develop children social-emotional competence, a positive and affectionate relationship between adults and children is very essential. Besides this, a positive relationship between teachers and young students helps those students to have better school achievement and behavioral skills. Teachers have the responsibility to enhance children's development in many aspects, including social, emotional, cognitive, academic, and behavioral skills. Various review studies show that SEC has direct influence on children's learning outcomes and on their ability to engage in good relationship. The purpose of this paper is to discuss the SEC on teacher- child relationship along with children's academic achievement, school readiness and behavioral success. With the help of several strategies of SEL teachers are able to build strong and healthy relationships with children. These strategies foster children's academic and behavioral success. Additionally, social and emotional learning is also defined in relation to school successes to show that competence in these areas increases students' reading, writing, critical thinking, and vocabulary skills.

Keywords: social-emotional competence, teacher-child relationship, school readiness, mental health, academic achievement, young children

Introduction

In every child's life there is a significant impact of teacher's teaching learning process on his all-round development from childhood to adulthood and in later stages of life as well. Young children are very sensitive, so teachers try to help them to build important social emotional skills. The teacher-child relationship must be examined in depth because many researchers have found strong links between these relationships and the children's behavior and academic success (Lippard, Paro, Rouse, & Crosby, 2018). Lippard et al. (2018) also found that strong teacher-child relationships help children to develop good behavioural skills and school success, cognitive, social, and emotional skills. In addition to ensuring strong and healthy teacher-child relationship, SEC also enhances the academic success, mental health and school readiness. Thus, in-depth examinations of the teacher-child relationship are essential.

Social and emotional skills also help children to live healthy and safe lives. Children need a long time to develop these skills, so teachers must develop children's social and emotional competence every day through the use of various activities in their early years. It is clear that social and emotional development within the early years of life is of great importance.

Concept of Social Emotional Competence

Social and emotional competence is a child's ability to interact in a positive way with others, communicate feelings positively and regulate behavior. A number of researchers have shown that children who enter kindergarten with more positive

profiles of social-emotional competence have not only more success in developing positive attitudes about school and successful early adjustment to school, but also improved grades and achievement (Birch, Ladd, & Blecher-Sass, 1997; Ladd, Birch, & Buhs, 1999; Ladd, Kochenderfer, & Coleman, 1996). Wu, Hu, Fan, Zhang, and Zhang (2018) considered social and emotional competence as the use of acceptable behavior to socialize with others and to foster positive interaction. Social emotional competence can be seen as an important protective factor for young children, buffering them from stressors and helping to prevent the development of serious emotional and behaviour difficulties in later life (Garnezy, 1991). Social emotional competence/well-being can be defined as cooperative and pro-social behaviour, initiation and maintenance of peer friendships and adult relationships, management of aggression and conflict, development of a sense of mastery and self-worth and emotional regulation and reactivity (Squires, 2002).

Social and emotional skills influence how children interact with others, how they deal with their emotions, and how they react to the events that happen around them. In addition, these social and emotional skills are correlated with the ability to properly express emotions such as happiness, sadness, nervousness, and anger; these skills also help children determine how to act when they feeling one of these emotions. In addition, children can learn about their own feelings and identities by practicing social and emotional skills with their peers and teachers. Thus, the development of SEC is

of key importance during early childhood for better learning outcomes, positive attitude and healthy relationships.

Sec and Teacher –Child Relationship

Teacher-child relationships play a pivotal role in education process. A positive relationship is essential to support children's development. Children personally enjoy interacting with teachers who are polite, kind, patient, flexible, creative, and dedicated. Early-childhood teachers thus need to have high-quality education along with social emotional competence skills. Moreover, parents of the young children also look for the best and kindest teachers who handle their children in a most affectionate way. (Lippard, Paro, Rouse, & Crosby, 2018) found that the teacher-child relationship must be examined in depth because there is strong links between these relationships and the children's behavior and academic success. Particularly in preschool and kindergarten, this relationship has a big impact on children's development; this impact lasts well into primary school (Lippard et al., 2018). Lippard et al. (2018) also declared that strong teacher-child relationships help children to develop good behavioural skills and school success, cognitive, social, and emotional skills. Graves and Howes (2011) declared that teachers' perceptions have a big impact on how they deal with students. The dynamic of the teacher-child relationship has a massive effect on children's school lives. (Brock & Curby, 2014) noted that close child-teacher relationships serve a governing function for children who engage in problematic behavior—helping, for example, in these children's social interactions. If the teacher-child relationship is not strong, the teacher cannot regulate the child's negative behavior, which could enhance the child's disconnection from social interactions (Brock & Curby, 2014). White (2015) stated that a good teacher-child relationship has many benefits for young children and that these benefits continue for a long time afterward. Children need to feel safe, flexible and comfortable with their teachers. Thus, teachers can develop a strong relationship with their students over time by showing respect, listening to them, talking to them, and making eye contact with them during their classroom activities. White (2015) found that preschool and kindergarten students who have healthy teacher-child relationships, as compared to those who do not, exhibit better peer communication in the classroom and have stronger overall social skills. White (2015) considered the teacher-child relationship in preschool and kindergarten to be related to the children's behavior and academic success in primary school. Similarly, children who do not have good relationships with their teachers in early childhood display less interaction with their peers, express more

disappointment, and show less tolerance of others, as compared to those with good relationships (White, 2015). Moreover, White showed that there is a connection between children's academic performance and their relationships with teachers: Children who had good relationships with early-childhood teachers later showed higher reading performance. Wu, Hu, Fan, Zhang, and Zhang (2018) explained that early childhood is a critical period because, at this stage, children begin to practice emotional control and sometimes are able to take time to deal with their emotions. Therefore, Teacher-child relationships also play a vital role in strengthening positive young children's behavioural skills, social skills, better academic performance and healthy relationship.

Sec and Academic Achievement

Academic achievement without social and emotional competence on the part of students is undesirable and rarely feasible (Zins, Elias, Greenberg, & Weissberg, 2000). Zins et al. (2000) believed we should expand beyond an academic focus to acknowledge the importance of educating knowledgeable, responsible and caring citizens, which requires systematic attention to children's social and emotional learning/competence. (Harniss, Epstein, Ruser, & Pearson, 1999) found that social-emotional competence influences academic growth and progress as children who feel competent, autonomous, and happy generally make good students. Children who are socially and emotionally well-adjusted do better at school, have increased confidence, have good relationships, take on and persist at challenging tasks and communicate well (National Research Council and Institutes of Medicine, 2000). Children who have limitations in their social-emotional development often demonstrate poor social, emotional and academic success (Aviles, Anderson, & Davila, 2005). Wu et al. (2018) mentioned that a warm and comfortable classroom climate with strong support from teachers is very effective at improving children's academic achievement; children in these environments show good behavior in class and interact well with others. Furthermore, teacher-child relationships are associated with many important aspects of life, including academic achievement, behavior, mental health, and physical health (Wu et al., 2018). There has been an explosion of interest in the development of Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) programs that seek to improve social health (e.g. high quality social support) and mental health (e.g. low suicidality, high life satisfaction, low depression; Elias, Hunter, & Kress, 2001). The regulation of pre-schoolers' emotions can predict their academic achievements through kindergarten and into the later school years (Denham, Bassett, Thayer et al., 2012). Social and emotional competence can also reinforce

and even enhance academic success (Denham, Bassett, Thayer et al., 2012).

Sec And School Readiness

Children spend a significant part of their day in school which makes the school environment a common point of entry to provide services and interventions to a large number of children. The school environment is a good avenue to identify children aimed at promoting social-emotional competence in the early years. Young children require healthy social-emotional development in order to be prepared and ready to learn once they enter school (Klein, 2002). Research has suggested that the pre-school years (4 to 6 years) are essential for building social emotional competence (Masten & Coatsworth, 1998). In addition, all children regardless of their risk level are engaged in a positive program within the school environment without the burden of potential stigmatization from other classmates. Wu, Hu, Fan, Zhang, and Zhang (2018) mentioned that developing children's social and emotional competence is essential to ensuring their readiness for school. According to Nix, Bierman, Domitrovich, and Gill (2013), the development of children's social and emotional competence directly influences their engagement in learning and thus facilitates their current and future academic achievement. In addition, to ensure strong academic achievement and high test scores, more social and emotional support for students is needed (Nix et al., 2013). Nix et al. (2013) indicated that, when children engage in social and emotional learning, starting in preschool, this improves their future learning engagement, academic success, and readiness for school.

According to Denham, Bassett, Thayer et al. (2012), many researchers have indicated that early-childhood social and emotional learning can promote children's cognitive development and enhance their classroom learning. Furthermore, social and emotional developmental skills are associated with children's failure or success in terms of sociability, school readiness, academic achievement, learning, and other challenges (Denham, Bassett, Thayer, et al., 2012). Collie, Martin, Nassar, and Roberts (2018) emphasized that, to be healthy (both inside and outside of school), children must have well-developed social and emotional competence. Collie et al. also demonstrated a positive connection between higher social and emotional competence and each of the following: higher academic outcomes, better school readiness, stronger educational engagement, higher rates of completing and continuing studies, and better well-being.

Intervention And Strategies To Foster Social Emotional Skills:

Children often face social and emotional difficulties due to the rapid development that takes place in early childhood. Though most young children eventually overcome these developmental difficulties, in many cases, such difficulties are predictive of future developmental instability. Research and practical advancements in the development, testing, and implementation of methods for ensuring positive social and emotional development have reduced the frequency of negative behavioral problems in early childhood (Poulou, 2013). With the help of various research-proven strategies and intervention children social and emotional development can be enhanced.

Promoting Alternative Thinking Strategies (PATHS). PATHS is an SEL program for preschool and elementary school designed to increase social and emotional competence; prevent violence, aggression, and other behavior problems; improve critical thinking skills, and enhance classroom climate (Greenberg, Kische, & Mihalic, 1998). Teachers using PATHS typically teach three 20-30 minute lessons per week. PATHS for the elementary level has been shown to: improve children's feelings vocabulary and their understanding of their own feelings and those of others and their verbal fluency; and reduce behavioural problems (Riggs, Greenberg, Kusche, & Pentz, 2006).

Responsive Classroom (RC) Approach. The RC approach is a way of teaching that integrates the social, emotional, and academic needs of children. RC includes ten classroom practices designed for both optimal learning and creating a classroom where children feel "safe, challenged, and joyful" (www.responsiveclassroom.org). RC impacts the social and emotional climate of the classroom, as well as student outcomes. Students in third to fifth grade classrooms that adopt RC report liking their school more and having more positive feelings toward learning, their teachers, and their classmates (Brock, Nishida, Chiong, Grimm, & Rimm-Kaufman, 2008).

The Reading, Writing, Respect, and Resolution (4Rs) Program. 4Rs trains teachers to use a literacy-based curriculum that includes lessons on conflict resolution, cultural difference, and cooperation (Durlak, Weissberg, Dymnicki, Taylor, & Schellinger, 2011).. 4Rs is designed to combine specific instructional, skill-building techniques and also model positive social norms for teacher-child warmth relationship.

Art-Based Approaches: Children should be encouraged to use art (whether copying, drawing, painting, or sculpting) to interact. Such activities help children to develop new ways of working and interacting (Laroche, 2015). According to Laroche

(2015) the teacher also explained that this was an opportunity for them to work and learn together.

The I Can Problem Solve Intervention: Many impact-based interventions exist for training young children in social and problem-solving skills. These interventions also are meant to decrease negative behaviors and increase academic achievement. Effective interventions should enhance young children's problem-solving skills from a multidimensional perspective—including cognition, emotion, and behavior. One such multidimensional program, which is based on cognitive problem-solving skills, is called I Can Problem Solve; this program addresses behaviors such as impulsiveness, inability to wait, aggressiveness, and frustration while promoting positive prosocial behaviors (Anliak & Sahin, 2010).

Teacher-Child Relationships: For young children, the healthy teacher-child relationship supports their ability to improve behavioral skills. Children who have bad relationships with their teachers have high levels of behavioral problems and low levels of competence (Pianta, 2004).

The RULER Approach to SEL. RULER is anchored in the achievement model of emotional literacy, which states that acquiring and valuing the knowledge and skills of recognizing, understanding, labelling, expressing, and regulating emotion (i.e., the RULER skills) is critical to youth development, academic engagement and achievement, and life success (Rivers & Brackett, 2011). RULER provides opportunities for adults and students to practice applying and modelling their RULER skills in ways that make emotions central to learning, teaching, and leading. (Taylor, Oberle, Durlak, & Weissberg, 2017) Learning tools and lessons are integrated into the standard academic curriculum from preschool through high school.

Conclusion

To sum up, social and emotional skills are related to communication skills and the ability to form healthy connections with people, at home and outside of school. Children need to learn various skills by interacting with their teachers and peers in order to develop their social and emotional competence. Social and emotional skills are fundamental, and the development of social and emotional competence leads to academic success and positive future learning. Moreover, young children with strong social and emotional skills can recognize and handle their behaviors in positive ways. The development of the social-emotional skills will lead to school readiness, adaption of future learning, well-being, and ability to manage good behaviors.

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